

Digital Preservation - Experiment Report

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Experiment Description

The experiment used here is pretty simple. Two different open data repositories have been chosen, namely the statistical federal office of germany and the open data repository of the United States of America. From each repository a dataset was chosen and the data got preprocessed to then get visualized in a JAVA application. The first input dataset contains over 6,56 million entries, so a mapreduce job got created which can be executed by running the ChicagoMapReducer.java class (providing the dataset location as first argument and the output path where to store the reduced file as second argument). With the reduced version the actual visualization can be done. Providing again the chicago dataset as first programm argument and then the second data set - crimes in germany, as second argument the FairDataScience.java class can be executed and will present the results.

Link to the repository: https://github.com/lucniner/digital_preservation_ex_1

DOI of the release: <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/125667644>

Input

Dataset 1 - Crimes in Chicago 2001 to present and Crimes in Chicago grouped by year

	Complete original Dataset	Grouped (processed) Dataset
Meta Data	https://data.cityofchicago.org/api/views/ijzp-q8t2	https://data.cityofchicago.org/api/views/ijzp-q8t2
Found on	data.gov (open data United States of America)	data.gov (open data United States of America)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1205219	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1205333

Dataset 2 - Crimes in Germany 1976 - 2016

Licence	No license information was provided.
Found on	https://www.destatis.de/DE/Startseite.html
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1205342

Libraries used

Apache Commons CSV
 Java Oracle JDK

Version 1.5 Licence: Apache 2.0
 Version 1.8 Licence: Oracle Binary Code License (BCL)

Output

The output of the experiment is a simple JAVA program which displays the data of the underlying data sources in a line chart. On the x-axis of the chart is the time and on the y-axis are the concrete values of each data series. The chart can be interpreted as the correlation between the two data sets.

Diagram

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Controller
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